

Etoricoxib, A Selective COX-2 Inhibitor

Igor Nelson*

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ABSTRACT: Etoricoxib is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) specific for cyclooxygenase enzyme 2 (COX-2) inhibition. It has approximately 106-fold selectivity for COX-2 inhibition over COX-1, so it can be useful to reduce gastrointestinal side effects commonly related with COX-1 inhibition. In this work, Etoricoxib is further analyzed following a pipeline for drug discovery, by performing conformer generation, analyzing electronic structure dependent properties, predicting docking with cyclooxygenase enzymes, calculating descriptors and searching publicly accessible databases for similar molecules. A method for finding similar molecules using RDKit descriptors and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is proposed. Docking was predicted by using MGLTools and AutoDock Vina and binding free energy scores were of -3.57 Kcal/mol and -10.81 Kcal/mol respectively for COX-1 and COX-2. We can conclude, as expected, that the molecule has a stronger binding affinity for COX-2 than for COX-1. By using the proposed method for finding similar compounds, it was possible to identify some molecules which may interact with COX-2 and not with COX-1. Their names are (1)tert-butyl (2-[[[2r]-3-oxo-2-[(propan-2-yl)amino]-3-[[pyridin-3-yl)methyl]amino}propyl]sulfonyl]ethyl)carbamate; (2)~{N}-[5-[(1~{S})-2-[[2~{S})-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)propan-2-yl]amino]-1-oxidanyl-ethyl]-2-oxidanyl-phenyl]methanamide; (3)1,1'-ethane-1,2-diylbis(3,7-dimethyl-3,7-dihydro-1h-purine-2,6-dione). These compounds could be potential targets as anti-inflammatory drugs, but further docking studies should be performed. Finally it was also possible to identify a similar molecule using ZINC database, with id ZINC216739553 and SMILES code Cc1cc2c3cc(S(C)(=O)=O)ccc3c3cc(Cl)cnc3c2cn1.

INTRODUCTION

Etoricoxib is a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) produced by McOLSON Research Laboratories that acts as a selective cyclooxygenase enzyme (COX) inhibitor, particularly inhibiting COX-2. It was patented in 1996 and approved for medical use in 2002¹. It is sold under the name Arcoxia and is currently approved in more than 80 countries, but not in the United States, where the Food and Drug Administration required additional safety and efficacy data for Etoricoxib approval.

Figure 1 shows a 2D representation of Etoricoxib. This drug is commonly indicated for the treatment of pain and inflammation due to rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, osteoarthritis, ankylosing spondylitis, chronic low back pain, acute pain, and gout². Most of its adverse effects are innocuous, but in some cases more serious problems are reported, such as fixed drug eruption and generalized erythema, acute generalized exanthematous pustulosis, erythema multiforme like eruption and drug induced pretibial erythema². It is important to note that it may increase the risk of heart attack, stroke, and other serious cardiovascular events².

Figure 1 Chemical Structure Depiction of Etoricoxib.

Humans have two forms of the cyclooxygenase enzyme: COX-1 and COX-2. A simplified paradigm stated that both were involved in the inflammatory processes, but only COX-1 would present beneficial effects. However, this is no longer valid. While COX-1 is known to be present in most of the tissues and has an important function maintaining the normal lining of the stomach and intestines, protecting these organs from the digestive juices. It is also necessary for correct kidney function and exerts action on the hemostatic/thrombogenic effects. On the other hand, COX-2 is primarily found at sites of inflammation and constitutively expressed in the brain, reproductive tissues and kidneys³. It plays an important role in the regulation of renal function. Inhibiting it, could make patients at risk of renal ischemia due to reduced vasodilatory prostaglandin synthesis⁴. On top of that, high uterine levels of COX-2 are necessary for the onset of labor and consequently the use of selective COX-2 inhibitors should be avoided in the early stages of pregnancy⁵.

Etoricoxib works by blocking the production of prostaglandins, in particular inhibiting COX-2 which is involved in the conversion of arachidonic acid to prostaglandin H₂, an important precursor of prostacyclin, expressed in inflammation. It has approximately 106-fold selectivity for COX-2 inhibition over COX-1⁶. This can be useful to reduce gastrointestinal side effects commonly related with COX-1 inhibition. However, note that because of the COX-2 “adaptative cytoprotection response” in GI mucosa, selective COX-2 inhibitors should be avoided in patients which already show gastric susceptibility⁷. Also, selective inhibition of COX-2 depletes prostacyclin, which acts as an atheroprotective agent, and not the COX-1 derived thromboxane A₂. That makes it act as a proaggregatory and vasoconstrictor mediator⁸. In that way, patients may be at a higher risk to heart attack and stroke. That is the reason why Etoricoxib and other COX-2 inhibitors have been so carefully studied.

In order to contribute to the field of study, Etoricoxib is further analyzed following a pipeline for drug discovery, by performing conformer generation, analyzing electronic structure dependent properties, analyzing docking with cyclooxygenase enzymes, calculating descriptors and searching publicly accessible databases for similar molecules. A method for finding similar molecules using descriptors and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is proposed and similar molecules are suggested.

METHODS

1. Conformer Generation

PubChem is the world’s largest collection of freely accessible chemical information. It allows to search chemicals by name, molecular formula, structure, and other identifiers⁶. All information regarding Etoricoxib such as canonical SMILES, 2D and 3D structures can be found at PubChem with compound CID 123619. It’s SMILES code is CC1=NC=C(C=C1)C2=C(C=C(C=N2)Cl)C3=CC=C(C=C3)S(=O)(=O)C.

In the present work 10 conformers were generated using OpenBabel software, a free, open-source software package designed to handle chemical data in various formats and perform a wide range of chemical-related tasks⁹. The method of choice was the Confab method. Using a systematic search strategy, this algorithm explores the conformational space and generates a diverse set of conformers capturing the relevant features of the molecule’s potential energy surface.

2. Energy Calculation

MOPAC is a software which calculates the effect of solvents on the electronic and molecular structure of a given molecule¹⁰. The algorithm of choice was the Parameterized Model number 7 (PM7), a computational method which uses modern semiempirical methods to calculate electronic structure dependent properties of molecules. One of its key parameters is the Electric Polarizability of the Surface (EPS). EPS values of 78.4 for water and 0.0 for vacuum were used in order to calculate each conformer’s structure. Values for final heat of formation were then collected for each molecule.

3. Docking

Protein Data Bank (PDB) provides a database of experimentally-determined 3D structures of proteins¹¹. Since there were no PDB models available proving binding of these molecules, several PDB structures were select from PDB in order to study docking.

- 6Y3C provides the crystalline structure of Human COX-1;
- 1EQG provides the crystalline structure of Ovine COX-1 bound to ibuprofen;
- 5KIR provides the crystalline structure of Human COX-2.

The MGLTools software suite, formerly known as the Molecular Graphics Laboratory, provides for visualization and analysis of molecular structures, as well as a useful framework for viewing bounding boxes and filetype conversion¹². As so, it was used in order to add polar hydrogens and convert between PDB and PDBQT, this file extension contains information about the charges and atomic solvation parameters of each atom in a molecular structure, which is necessary for performing molecular docking simulations.

For COX-1, the strategy was to align 6Y3C with 1EQG in order to find the most probable binding pocket and then using MGLTools and AutoDock Vina^{13,14}, an open-source program for doing molecular docking, in order to predict accurate docking. Regarding COX-2, 5KIR provides already the structure of Rofecoxib, a similar molecule, bound to it. So here there was no need to align, just to use the same software in order to compare docking results.

In the Annex 1. Docking Parameters you can find more information with the parameters used for MGLTools and AutoDock Vina.

4. Descriptor Extraction

RDKit, an open-source software package for cheminformatics and molecular modeling¹⁵, was used for extracting descriptors from Etoricoxib molecule. Such features can describe the molecule in different dimensions. Zero dimensional (0D) features refer to molecular descriptors that do not depend on the molecule’s topology, but rather on its atomic composition. One dimensional (1D) used to describe the structural features of molecules and take into account the molecular topology and are calculated based on the atom and bond properties within a molecule. Two dimensional (2D) and three dimensional (3D) features take into account structure of a molecule, including the positions and bonds of atoms. Finally, four dimensional (4D) features combine the 3D structure with electronic properties giving information regarding the dynamic behavior of the molecule. Molecular fingerprinting represents the structural features of a molecule in a simplified and computationally efficient manner.

5. Finding Similar Molecules

In order to find similar molecules, a series of descriptors, as shown in the Annex 2. Features Extracted with RDKit. They were extract for Etoricoxib and for the whole Ligand Expo Database¹⁶. Ligand Expo provides chemical and struc-

tural information about small molecules within the structure entries of the PDB. After dropping some missing values, the final ligand database had 39866 molecules.

In order to scan Ligand Expo for molecules similar to Etoricoxib, a strategy was implemented consisting in data normalization and PCA with 3 components. Molecules were projected into 3D space and distances were measured between Etoricoxib and a selected amount of the closest ones.

Zinc Database, curated collection of commercially available chemical compounds prepared especially for virtual screening¹⁷, was also scanned for similar molecules.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

1. Conformer Generation

Conformers are different spatial arrangements of a ligand molecule. In the process of drug discovery, they are very important since they affect the binding affinity between each candidate molecule and the target protein. These conformers can also provide insight into the bioactive conformation of a molecule.

Figure 2 depicts the conformers generated using Open Babel with Confab Method. It is possible to see that the algorithm explored the spatial arrangements mainly by applying rotations to the sulfonamide group (-SO₂NH₂) and to the aromatic ring containing the methyl group. The angles formed by the backbone were similar in all the generated molecules.

Figure 2 10 Etoricoxib conformers generated using Open Babel Software with Confab Method.

2. Energy Calculation

The minimum energy conformation of a drug candidate, may give insights into its shape, orientation, and stability, helping to design and optimize drugs. The final heat of formation is the amount of heat absorbed or released when one mole of a compound is formed from its constituent elements. They can be positive or negative depending on whether the formation of the compound is endothermic or exothermic respectively.

For each conformer MOPAC calculations were made using PM7 and final heat of formation is shown in Table 1. There wasn't a big variance between the values. The average for water was -41,29 (Kcal/Mol) with the lowest being 8 with -41,80 (Kcal/Mol). In vacuum average value was 22,27 (Kcal/Mol) with lowest being the 8 with 18,26 (Kcal/Mol). In practical terms, it is unlikely that a reaction would occur under vacuum conditions as there would be no driving force for the reaction to take place. Therefore, conformer 8 was

used for the following steps of this work, and further studied regarding docking and feature and descriptor extraction.

Table 1 Final Heat of Formation for Each Conformer

Conformer	Final Heat of Formation (Kcal/Mol)	
	Water	Vacuum
0	-41,32	23,06
1	-41,25	23,10
2	-41,05	22,43
3	-41,09	23,24
4	-41,31	22,37
5	-41,65	22,41
6	-41,39	22,32
7	-40,82	18,26
8	-41,80	22,33
9	-41,30	23,19

3. Docking

After choosing the lowest energy conformer, a study was made regarding its docking with both cyclooxygenases. **Figure 3** shows how the binding boxes were placed using MGLTools. The center of the box was manually adjusted in order to be placed near the known ligand position. Despite being similar, the structure varies among these molecules. The inhibitor binding site in COX-2 is 25% larger than that in COX-1¹⁸.

Figure 3 The binding boxes set for each one of the enzymes. On left COX-1. On right COX-2. The green molecules at the center correspond to the ligands found in the corresponding crystalline structures. Ibuprofen and Rofecoxib respectively.

Using AutoDock Vina, it was possible to find the best candidate position for binding with both molecules. **Figure 4** depicts, on left, overlapping of the homologue from Ovine (grey) with the Human COX-1 (cyan and pink). Note that the grey ligand is Ibuprofen and the colored one is the best mode calculated with Vina. On right, the best mode for binding with Human COX-2, here the grey corresponds to Rofecoxib which is a very similar molecule. The ligand molecules were not used for docking, just for finding the bounding box.

Table 1 shows the scores for the best 12 modes of binding between Etoricoxib and both cyclooxygenases. As expected, Etoricoxib is a specific COX-2 inhibitor and the binding free energy is much lower for that enzyme. That is verifiable not just for the best match, but in the overall scores. Note that almost half of the modes for COX-1 show positive scores,

while for COX-2 they are all negative. On top of that, the worst mode for COX-2 stills shows a better score than the best for COX-1. In this case, the free energy scores for binding of best candidates with COX-1 and COX-2 are -3.57 Kcal/mol and -10.81 Kcal/mol respectively. Note that the more negative the free energy score, the stronger the binding affinity between the molecule and the enzyme.

Figure 4 The best modes for docking calculated with each enzyme. COX-1 on left, COX-2 on right.

Table 2 Binding Free Energy Between Etoricoxib and Both Cyclooxygenases.

COX-1		COX-2	
Mode	Kcal/Mol	Mode	Kcal/Mol
1	-3,57	1	-10,81
2	-3,45	2	-10,41
3	-3,44	3	-9,52
4	-2,02	4	-9,07
5	-1,79	5	-8,43
6	-0,24	6	-8,29
7	0,2	7	-7,87
8	0,24	8	-5,36
9	0,49	9	-5,21
10	0,54	10	-5,12
11	0,59	11	-5,05
12	1,87	12	-4,98

4. Finding Similar Molecules

After normalization and PCA analysis in 3 components, the molecules were projected in 3D space. In the left side of Figure 5, all the 39866 points created a cloud in which is challenging to identify distances. Because of that, the 500 most similar to Etorixocib, in order words, the ones which had a closest Euclidean distance, were selected and the three most similar were identified.

Figure 5 - A 3D representation of the descriptors extracted for each molecule in relationship to Etoricoxib (in center). On the left a representation of all molecules is shown. On right the 500 most similar are select and 3 nearest ones are colored in red.

The 2D structure of these 3 molecules is shown in Figure 6. Their names are, from left, to right:

- tert-butyl (2-[[{(2r)-3-oxo-2-[(propan-2-yl)amino]-3-[[pyridin-3-yl)methyl]amino]propyl]sulfanyl]ethyl)carbamate
- ~{N}-[5-[[{1~{S}}]-2-[[{2~{S}}]-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)propan-2-yl]amino]-1-oxidanyl-ethyl]-2-oxidanyl-phenyl]methanamide
- 1,1'-ethane-1,2-diylbis(3,7-dimethyl-3,7-dihydro-1h-purine-2,6-dione)

Overall, it is possible to see that they have some similar characteristics to Etoricoxib. The importance of this compounds relies on the fact that they may interact with COX-2. For that, further docking studies with this enzymne should be made.

Finally, the ZINC database was analyzed for similar molecules. Most molecules found, such as etoricoxib 1'-n'-oxide, are altered forms of Etoricoxib. But it was possible to identify a molecules ZINC216739553 which is similar and is available for sale. It's 2D structure is shown in Figure 7. Its chemical structure is represented by the SMILES code Cc1cc2c3cc(S(C)(=O)=O)ccc3c3cc(Cl)cnc3c2cn1.

Figure 6 The 3 molecules most similar to Etoricoxib found with this method.

Figure 7 Chemical Structure Depiction of ZINC216739553.

CONCLUSIONS

The negative value of the heat of formation in water suggests that the molecule is more stable in water than in a vacuum, which is consistent with the fact that many molecules are more stable in a solvent environment. The difference in heat of formation between water and vacuum indicates that the solvation effect plays a significant role in the stability of the molecule. When the molecule is in water, it interacts with water molecules through hydrogen bonding and other electrostatic interactions. These interactions can affect the stability and properties of the molecule.

Free energy scores for binding of best candidates with COX-1 and COX-2 are of -3.57 Kcal/mol and -10.81 Kcal/mol respectively. From these scores, we can conclude that the molecule has a stronger binding affinity for COX-2 than for COX-1. This is because the free energy score for COX-2 is more negative than that for COX-1, indicating that more energy is released when the molecule binds to COX-2 than when it binds to COX-1.

Overall, these results suggest that the molecule may be more effective in inhibiting COX-2 than COX-1, which could have implications for its potential use as a therapeutic agent for conditions such as inflammation and pain. However, is important to remember that, among other negative side effects and interactions, selective inhibition of COX-2 depletes prostacyclin, an atheroprotective agent. In that way, patients may be at a higher risk to heart attack and stroke.

By using PCA of a set of descriptors extracted with RDKit, it was possible to identify three molecules which may interact with COX-2 and not with COX-1. Their names are (1)tert-butyl (2-[[[(2r)-3-oxo-2-[[propan-2-yl]amino]-3-[[pyridin-3-yl)methyl]amino]propyl]sulfanyl]ethyl]carbamate; (2)~{N}-[5-[[1~{S}]-2-[[[2~{S}]-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)propan-2-yl]amino]-1-oxidanyl-ethyl]-2-oxidanyl-phenyl]methanamide; (3)1,1'-ethane-1,2-diylbis(3,7-dimethyl-3,7-dihydro-1h-purine-2,6-dione). These compounds could be potential targets as anti-inflammatory drugs. However, further studies would be needed to confirm these findings and explore the mechanism of action of the molecule.

Lastly, it was also possible to identify a similar molecule using ZINC database, with id ZINC216739553 and SMILES code Cc1cc2c3cc(S(C)(=O)=O)ccc3c3cc(Cl)cnc3c2cn1.

ANNEXES

1. Docking Parameters

For COX-1 the searching box was placed at (26.639, 34.095, 199.788), (x,y,z) respectively, with a size of (15,15,15). For COX-2 the searching box was placed at (22.940, 0.937, 34.671), (x,y,z) respectively, with a size of (15,15,15). For both studies, the parameters for Autodock Vina were set with an exhaustiveness of 500, energy range of 10 and number of modes equal to 20.

2. Features Extracted with RDKit

Descriptors extracted for each molecule using RDKit were Molecular Weight, Heavy Atom Count, Number of Hydrogen Donors, Number of Hydrogen Acceptors, Number of Rotatable Bonds, Number of Rings, Number of Aromatic Rings,

Number of Atoms, Number of Stereo Centers, Number of Unspecified Atom Stereo Centers, Molecular LogP, BalabanJ, BertzCT, Kappa1, TPSA, Wiener Index, TPSA per Volume, Asphericity, Eccentricity, PMI1, PMI2, PMI3, Sphericity Index, DipoleMoment1, DipoleMoment2 and DipoleMoment3.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

1. Corresponding Author

*Corresponding author(s): Igor Nelson, Departamento de Ciências da Vida, Universidade de Coimbra, CC. E-mail: igornelson5@hotmail.com,

ABBREVIATIONS

NSAID, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug; COX, Cyclooxygenase; PCA, Principal Component Analysis; PM7, Parameterized Model number 7; EPS, Electric Polarizability of the Surface; PDB, Protein Databank; 3D, 3rd Dimension.

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